

Effects of Mastery and Collaborative Learning ... (Isah, et. al., 2023) DOI:

Effects of Mastery and Collaborative Learning Approaches on Performance in Concept Genetics among Secondary School Students in Katsina State

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Abstract

A paradigm and theoretical shift in instructional designs and teaching methodologies has been witnessed in the 20th and 21st centuries, where effective teaching approaches were designed to suit learners' disposition because, educators realized the ways students preferred to be taught is significant with respect to students' academic performance. The study therefore investigated the effect of mastery and collaborative learning approaches on performance in concepts genetics among senior secondary school students in Katsina State, using gender and self-concept as moderating variables. The study adopted $3 \times 2 \times 2$ pretest posttest randomized quasi experimental factorial design. The first and second experimental and the control groups were treated using mastery learning, collaborative learning and traditional lecture methods respectively. Genetics Performance Test (Cronbach $\alpha = 0.802$) and Students' Self-concept Questionnaire (Cronbach $\alpha = 0.661$) were used to collect data which were analyzed using ANCOVA. The results of the study revealed that, there is significant main effect of treatment (mastery and collaborative learning) on students' performance in genetics concept ($F_{1, 96} = 27.513; p < 0.05$). However, the main and interaction effects of the treatments and moderating variables were not significant. Based on these findings, it was concluded that, mastery and collaborative learning approaches have equivalent effects on students' performance in genetics concept. It was also recommended that teachers of biology should expose students to collaborative learning strategies in other to encourage social interaction among learners and use formative evaluation and remedial activities to help the so-called weak students gain mastery of learning contents.

Keyword: Mastery Learning, Collaborative Learning, Gender, Self-concept, Performance, Genetics Concept

Introduction

A paradigm and theoretical shift in instructional designs and teaching methodologies has been witnessed in the 20th and 21st centuries. Effective teaching approaches tailored to suit learners' disposition were observed because educators realized the ways students preferred to be taught is significant with respect to students' academic performance. Mastery Learning Approach (MLA) is one of such teaching approaches postulated in the 20th century by Benjamin Blooms. MLA is an instructional model based on the assertion that, if students are given enough time and attention while using appropriate teaching methods, most students can master any learning objective (Guskey, 2022). In MLA approach, students must achieve a level of mastery between 80-90% on a knowledge test in prerequisite knowledge before moving forward to learn subsequent information. This means that, every student is given the chance to learn and achieve mastery level at his/her own pace. Therefore, MLA can be used to improve students' understanding of perceived abstract concepts like genetics. Empirical studies conducted on mastery learning revealed the potential of the teaching strategy to enhance students' performance. For instance, Adeniji, *et al* (2018) investigated the effect of mastery learning on senior secondary school students' achievement in circle geometry and revealed that students' achievement in Geometry was enhanced significantly. In another study, Cheta and Chidinma (2018) compared Mastery and Constructivist-Based learning approach and concluded that, mastery learning

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approach is a better instructional approach than constructivist-based learning. Nnorom and Uchegbu (2017) also finds out that, mastery learning approach is effective in enhancing students' achievement in biology. Another instructional approach which has now being emphasized in teaching is collaborative learning. Collaborative learning approach is a strategy of learning in which, learners interact in smaller groups with the objective to collectively understand concept (Anthony, *et al*, 2018). In collaborative learning approach, learners with different characteristics are aggregated into heterogeneous groups. Learners in a collaborative group work together, exchange ideas, knowledge, experience and foster team spirit and cooperation among themselves. The learners also solve any problem collectively and clarify any ambiguity in concepts. In this sense, learners have full autonomy on their learning while the teacher only serves as a facilitator of the learning process.

Collaborative learning is characterized by positive interdependence (Oyarole, 2016). In positive interdependence, learners in collaborative group perceive that success or failure depends on their collective group work (Kaliisa, *et al*, 2022). If the group performs well, every individual in the group performs well and vice versa. For this reason, the attainment of personal goals depends on active participation of everyone in the group for success of the entire group (Oyarole, 2016). Collaborative learning approach promotes interaction among students around appropriate tasks and increases their mastery of critical concepts (Haataja, *et al* 2022). When students relate with other students, they learn to explain, discuss and respect other's perspectives, which lead to greater understanding of the learning materials. The process of resolving differences in opinion in collaborative activities result in the development of higher levels of understanding (Troussas, *et al*, 2023). Anthony, *et al* (2018) compared collaborative, individualistic and demonstration learning strategies using 155 senior secondary school students as sample. The study revealed that, collaborative learning strategy is more effective in enhancing students' academic performance compared to individualistic or demonstration learning strategy. Iji, *et al* (2017) investigated the effect of collaborative instructional strategy on chemistry achievement using a sample of 216 students in senior secondary school chemistry in Benue State, Nigeria. The researchers revealed that, students in the experimental group have a significant higher mean score than those in the control group. Williams and Akpan (2017) and Oyarole (2016) revealed a significant effect of collaborative learning on academic performance in biology.

Researchers have developed interest on the main and interaction effects of students' personality traits and treatments on dependents variables. Self-concept is one of such students' personality traits that has repeatedly found to have influence on academic performance. Self-concept is the perception a person has upon him/herself. It is conceptualized as "self-identity" which involves a mental and conceptual awareness and persistent regard that a person holds about his/her own being (Perinelli, *et al*, 2022). Self-concept is a product of social interaction developed through interpersonal relationship and striving for consistency (Arens, *et al*, 2022). In this recent time, self-concept has now been used as a moderating variable (Carter & Vartanian, 2022; Caasi & Pentang, 2022) due to its possible interference in experimental studies involving students' academic skills. This is because, students with better academic self-concept tends to have confidence and better academic performance. Therefore, including self-concept as a moderating variable in experimental studies like this study will help to annul the effect of extraneous effect of self-concept. There is an increased interest in male and female students' participation in Science Education because of gender imbalance in science education (Ogunode, *et al*, 2023; Eyiuche, 2019). Gender has now mostly been included in empirical studies as moderating variables. Some previous studies have shown that, gender is a significant factor for students' performance in science with either male or female students outperforming the other (Cheta & Chidinma, 2018; Udo & Udofia, 2014). However, some studies showed that, gender has no significant influence on students' performance in science (Nnorom and Uchegbu, 2017; Olatoye, 2017; Lamidi, *et al*, 2015). This study therefore included gender as a second moderating variable.

Genetics, an aspect of biology, is the scientific study of heredity and variation among living things. Students perceive genetics as too abstract and difficult to learn (Agbowuro, *et al*, 2016; Agboghroma & Oyovwi, 2015). As such, students woefully fail questions on genetics aspect of Biology in external examinations (WAEC, 2019; 2018; 2017). Students' specific weakness as reported by WAEC Chief Examiner include inability to demonstrate crossing to produce offspring; wrong usage of genetic symbols and inappropriate use of technical terms to describe genetic process. It has been stated that, MLA and other constructivists' learning approaches such as collaborative learning approach are recommended to effectively teach biology, most teachers remain adamant and thus rely heavily on traditional method such as lecture (chalk and talk) method which promote rote learning and make the teaching of biological concepts less effective. Students' performance has always been the most vital yardstick for the measurement of the effectiveness of instructional approach and the school system. The level of students' performance is determined by the learning situation more of which depends on the instructional approach. For any instructional approach to be effective, it must improve the students' performance in concept learned and as well enhances application of learning experience to other similar concepts. The quest to discover effective instructional approach to enhance

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students' performance in biological concepts has been a long-time struggle. The dwindling students' performance in biology and the manner students respond to questions in different aspects of biology and genetics in particular have shown that, there is problem in the instructional approach in biology classrooms. Against this problem therefore, the study investigated the effect of mastery and collaborative learning approaches on students' performance in genetics concepts using self-concept and gender as moderating variables.

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of the study are to:

1. Examine the main effect of treatment on students' performance in genetics concept.
2. Find out the main effect of gender on students' performance in genetics concept.
3. Determine the main effect of self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.
4. Assess the interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' performance in genetics concept.
5. Examine the interaction effect of treatment and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.
6. Measure the interaction effect of gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.
7. Examine the interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. There is no significant main effect of treatment on students' performance in genetics concept.
2. There is no significant main effect of gender on students' performance in genetics concept.
3. There is no significant main effect of self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.
4. There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' performance in genetics concept.
5. There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.
6. There is no significant interaction effect of gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.
7. There is no significant interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concept.

Methodology

This study adopted a 3×2×2 pre-test post-tests randomized quasi experimental factorial design. This design was adopted because the independent variables can be manipulated. Also, factorial design helped to check the main and interaction effect of independent and moderating variables on the dependent variable. The detail of the research design is clearly summarized in Tables 1 and 2:

Table 1: Randomized Quasi-Experimental Control Group Pre-test Post-test Design

Group	Pre-test	Treatment	Post-test
1 st Experimental group	O _{1ML}	X _{ML}	O _{2ML}
2 st Experimental group	O _{1Coll}	X _{Coll}	O _{2Coll}
Control	O _{1L}		O _{2L}

Key: O_{1ML} represents pre-test for mastery learning group (1st experimental group)
 X_{ML} represents treatment for Mastery learning group (1st experimental group)
 O_{2ML} represents post-test for Mastery learning group (1st experimental group)
 O_{1Coll} represents pre-test for collaborative learning group (2nd experimental group)
 X_{Coll} represents treatment for collaborative learning group (2nd experimental group)
 O_{2Coll} represents post-test for collaborative learning group (2nd experimental group)
 O_{1L} represents pre-test for control group method
 O_{2L} represents post-test for control group method

Table 2: Randomized Pre-test Post-tests Factorial Design

Group	Male		Female		Total
	High Self-Concept	Low Self-Concept	High Self-Concept	Low Self-Concept	
ML	8	8	8	8	32
CL	8	8	8	8	32

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Control	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Total							96

Key: ML is Mastery learning group; CL is Collaborative learning group

The population for this study comprises 12,853 (6079 male and 6774 female) senior secondary three (SS3) students in Katsina Education Zonal Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria. Katsina Zonal Education consists of 25 secondary schools spread across three Local Government Areas: Katsina, Kaita and Jibiya Local Government Area. A multistage sampling technique was employed in selecting the respondents. A cluster sampling was used to select three schools, one school from each Local Government. The three schools were randomly assigned as experimental and control groups. A simple random sampling technique was used to select thirty-two students from each school. Thus, the total sample size of the study consists of 96 students. In this study, Genetics Performance Test (GPT), and Self-Concept Questionnaire (SCQ) were used to collect data.

Genetics Performance Test (GPT) is a twenty-five (25) item multiple-choice objective questions developed by the researcher. The items in GPT were constructed reflecting five selected topics in genetics aspect of secondary school biology curriculum. These topics are: 1) Chromosomes as the basis of heredity; 2) Transmission and Expression of Characters; 3) Sex determination in human beings, 4) Sex linkages in human beings and 5) Application of the principles of heredity. Each question in GPT was scored one mark. Self-Concept Questionnaire SCQ is a researcher-developed fifteen (15) items, four-point Likert-type scale instrument calibrated with Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). For all positive items on the scale, SA was assigned 4 points, A was assigned 3 points, D was assigned 2 points and SD was assigned 1 point. The maximum and minimum obtainable points are 60 and 15 respectively. Scores below 37 were categorized as low self-concept while scores from 38 above were categorized as high self-concept.

The initial drafts of the instruments were validated by two experienced biology teachers and an expert in psychometrics to check the relevance, adequacy and structure of the items before the pretest. The content validity of GPT was ascertained following strictly the number of items per topic as specified in the test blueprint in table 3 below. The recommendations and suggestions made by the experts were used to modify the final draft of the instruments.

Table 3: Table of Specification of 25 items Genetics Performance Test (GPT)

Content	Weight	Remember	Understand	Apply	Analyze	Evaluate	Total
Chromosomes; the basis of heredity	22%	3	2	0	0	0	5
Transmission and expression of character in organisms.	26%	2	2	1	2	1	8
Sex determination in human beings	15%	0	2	1	0	0	3
Sex linkage in human beings	15%	-	-	-	1	2	3
Application of the principles of heredity	22%	1	1	2	1	1	6
Total	100%	6	7	4	4	4	25

Item Analysis (Difficulty Index and Discrimination Power) of GPT

The items on GPT were analyzed by determining the Difficulty Index (d) and Discrimination Power (D) of GPT using the pilot sample performance. Items with difficulty index between 30 – 70% were accepted while items with difficulty index above 70% or below 30% was tagged too easy or too difficult respectively and reviewed accordingly. For Discrimination Power (D), items within the range of 0.7 – 0.3 were retained and used for the study while discriminating power outside this range were reviewed.

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The reliability coefficient of GPT and SCQ were determined using Cronbach alpha method of estimating internal consistency. The data from a pilot study conducted was used to determine the reliability of GPT and SCQ which was found to be 0.802 and 0.661 respectively. The data collected were analyzed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). SPSS version 23 was used to carry out the analysis.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant main effect of treatment on students' performance in genetics concepts.

Table 4: ANCOVA of Effects of Treatment on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Treatment	1159.847	2	579.923	27.513	.000	Sig.
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

a. R Squared = .511 (Adjusted R Squared = .441); Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Table 4 shows the main effects of treatment on students' academic performance in biology. There is significant main effect of treatment on students' performance in genetics concepts ($F_{2, 96} = 27.513$; $p < 0.05$). This means that, the teaching strategies experimented has a significant effect in enhancing the students' performance in genetics concepts. As such, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant main effect of treatment on students' performance in genetics concepts is rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant main effect of gender on students' performance in genetics concepts.

Table 5: Main Effects of Gender on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Gender	29.429	1	29.429	1.396	.241	NS
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

In Table 5, there is no significant main effect of gender on students' academic performance in genetics concepts ($F_{1, 96} = 1.396$; $p > 0.05$). This means that, the teaching strategies experimented in this study has nothing to do with students' gender. Both male and female students can perform equally when these teaching strategies are used. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant main effect of gender on students' performance in genetics concepts is hereby retained.

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Hypothesis 3

There is no significant main effect of self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts.

Table 6: Main Effects of Selfconcept on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Selfconcept	3.693	1	3.693	.175	.677	NS
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Analysis in Table 6 shows that, there is no significant main effect of self-concept on students' academic performance in genetics concepts ($F_{1, 96} = 0.175$; $p > 0.05$). This means that, the students performed equally in genetics concepts irrespective of the level of their self-concepts. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant main effect of self-concept on students' performance in biology is hereby retained.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' performance in genetics concepts

Table 7: Interaction Effects of Treatment and Gender on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Treatment * Gender	25.367	2	12.684	.602	.550	NS
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

In Table 7, the two-way interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' performance in genetics concepts is not significant ($F_{2, 96} = 0.602$; $p > 0.05$). This means that, the efficacy of the teaching strategies experimented in this study does not depend on students' gender. Both male and female students performed equally when taught genetics concepts using MLA and CLA. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' performance in genetics concepts is retained.

Hypothesis 5

There is no significant interaction effect of treatment and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts.

Table 8: Two-Way Interaction Effects of Treatment and Self-concept on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.

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Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Treatment * Selfconcept	46.534	2	23.267	1.104	.336	NS
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Data analysis in Table 8 revealed that, the two-way interaction effect of treatment and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts is not significant ($F_{2, 96} = 1.104$; $p > 0.05$). This means that, the efficacy of the teaching strategies experimented in this study is independent on students' self-concept. Students with low or high self-concepts will perform equally when exposed to genetics concepts. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant interaction effect of treatment and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts is therefore retained.

Hypothesis 6

There is no significant interaction effect of gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts.

Table 9: Two-Way Interaction Effects of Gender and Self-concept on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of			F	Sig.	Remark
	Squares	df	Mean Square			
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Gender * Self-concept	3.643	1	3.643	.173	.679	NS
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

The two-way interaction effect of gender and self-concept on students' performance in biology in Table 9 is not significant ($F_{1, 96} = 0.173$; $p > 0.05$). This means that, the interplay between students' gender and their self-concept will not affect their performance when taught genetics concepts using MLA and CLA. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant interaction effect of gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts is therefore retained.

Hypothesis 7

There is no significant interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts.

Table 10: Three-Way Interaction Effects of Treatment, Gender and Self-concept on Students' Performance in Genetics Concepts

Source	Type III Sum of			F	Sig.	Remark
	Squares	df	Mean Square			
Corrected Model	1831.842 ^a	12	152.653	7.242	.000	Sig.
Intercept	1543.916	1	1543.916	73.247	.000	Sig.
Pretest	132.907	1	132.907	6.305	.014	Sig.
Treatment * Gender * Self-concept	32.334	2	16.167	.767	.468	NS
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			
Total	37632.000	96				
Corrected Total	3581.333	95				

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Sig=Significant ($p < 0.05$); NS=Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Result in Table 10 revealed that, the three-way interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts is not significant ($F_{2, 96} = 0.767$; $p > 0.05$). This finding clearly defines the efficacy of the teaching strategies experimented as independent on students' gender and self-concept. As such, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant interaction effect of treatment, gender and self-concept on students' performance in genetics concepts is therefore retained. In a nutshell, the main effect of the treatment on students' performance in biology is significant but the main and interaction effects of the moderating variables (gender and self-concept) on the students' performance in biology are not significant. The teaching strategies experimented in this study as a whole accounted for 51.1% of the variation in the students' performance in genetics concepts ($R^2 = 0.511$; $F_{12, 95} = 7.242$; $p < 0.05$) (Table 4). However, it is important to determine the significance of the mean difference in the students' performance since the three groups performed differently. This is why Table 11 is presented.

Table 11: Univariate Tests of Mean Scores of the Experimental and Control Groups

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Contrast	1159.847	2	579.923	27.513	.000	*Sig.
Error	1749.492	83	21.078			

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

In Table 11, there is significant mean difference in performance among MLA, CLA and the Lecture Method groups ($F_{2, 83} = 27.513$; $p < 0.05$). This means that, the three groups performed at different levels. By comparing the groups 2×2 pairwise will help revealed the group that produced the difference. Table 12 therefore shows the comparison among the groups.

Table 12: Pairwise Comparisons of Experimental and Control Groups

Treatment	(J) Treatment	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	Remark
MLA	CLA	-1.552	1.309	.717	**NS
	Lecture Method	7.714*	1.347	.000	*Sig
CLA	MLA	1.552	1.309	.717	**NS
	Lecture Method	9.267*	1.323	.000	*Sig
Lecture Method	MLA	-7.714*	1.347	.000	*Sig
	CLA	-9.267*	1.323	.000	*Sig

*Significant ($p < 0.05$); **Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

In Table 12, there is no significant difference between MLA and CLA (Mean Difference = -1.552; $p > 0.05$). However, there is significant difference between MLA and Lecture Method (Mean Difference = 7.714; $p < 0.05$). Also, there is significant difference between CLA and Lecture Method (Mean Difference = 9.267; $p < 0.05$). It can therefore be inferred that, MLA and CLA are the causes of the difference produced in the students' performance in genetics concepts. As such, MLA and CLA are effective in teaching genetics concepts.

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed that, there is a significant main effect of mastery learning approach on students' performance in genetics concepts. This finding agrees with the findings of Adeniji, *et al* (2018) and Cheta and Chidinma (2018) that mastery learning approach has significant effect on students' academic achievement. Many other previous studies conducted on mastery learning also proved the efficacy of this teaching method (Mitee & Obaitan, 2015; Udo & Udofia, 2014). This finding is therefore not a surprise because the formative assessment used as diagnostic tool do not only help weak learners achieve instructional objectives but it also helps to bridge the gap between the students with high and low self-concept (Guskey, 2022). The study further revealed that, there is significant main effect of collaborative learning approach on students' performance in genetics concepts. This finding corroborates with the findings of Anthony, *et al* (2018), Iji, *et al* (2017) that collaborative learning approach has significant effect on students' academic achievement. Collaborative learning approach has been proved to be an efficient teaching method in some aspects in biology (Williams & Akpan, 2017; Oyarole, 2016). This finding is not shocking because, collaborative learning has been theorized as a group-based learning process where students can reach their

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level of potential development through positive interdependency which characterized the model. Both mastery and collaborative learning has equal effect on students' performance in genetics concepts. In collaborative learning, students are more involved in the learning process. They interact and share common goal of success. This process gives strength to the weak students and thus enhanced performance. However, in mastery learning, students are less involved. But the corrective measures and the enrichment activities used after diagnosing students' strength and weakness enhance students' performance. Students could attain their level of potential development with either learning by collaboration or by learning for mastery.

Another finding of this study is that, there is no significant main effect of gender on students' performance in genetics concepts. Also, there is no significant two-way interaction effect of gender and treatment on students' performance in genetics concepts. This finding corresponds with the findings of Olatoye (2017) that, gender has no main nor interaction effects on treatment. Since the main and interaction effect of gender with treatment are not significant, it means that, the treatment is gender friendly. The innate difference in gender is not based on aptitude but on the nature of chromosome an individual inherits before birth. This cannot be translated into the learning process.

The study further revealed that, one-way and two-way interaction effect of self-concept and treatment on students' performance in genetics concepts are not significant. This finding agrees with the findings of Olatoye (2017) that, self-concept has no main effect nor interaction effects on treatment. It has been asserted that, effective teaching strategies do not only influence students' academic performance (Williams & Akpan, 2017; Enohuan, 2015) but also influence students' enabling variables such as attitude, interest, motivation to learning/study habit and also self-concept (Ukor & Isah, 2015; Enohuan, 2015). In mastery learning, students' learning difficulties are identified through diagnostic evaluation and corrected using remedial programmes. In the collaborative learning strategy, students with low aptitude and/or low self-concepts are grouped with students with high aptitude and/or high self-concept. In these kinds of learning process, both low and high self-concept students can attain the level of potential development and perform well in schools. This is why the one, two and three-ways effect of treatment with moderating variables on the students' performance are not significant.

Conclusion

Students' mode of response to questions on genetics concepts and performance in biology as a whole has not been encouraging despite efforts being made to stimulate the intellectual skill and personal growth of the students in science. The major cause of the poor performances in biology is attributed to the use of inappropriate instructional strategies adopted by the biology teachers. However, this study provides an empirical support and credence to mastery and collaborative learning as efficient enough to raise students' performance beyond the present level. Both mastery and collaborative learning strategies facilitates students' performance better than the traditional lecture methods. Remarkably as these learning strategies are, gender and self-concept do not affect students' performance when they are used. It is revealed that, the treatment given to the three groups have significant effects on academic performance though, students in the mastery and collaborative learning groups performed higher than those in the control/lecture groups. It is hereby concluded that, mastery and collaborative learning strategy have significant effect on the students' performance in genetics concepts than the traditional lecture method.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following are hereby recommended:

1. Teachers of biology should expose students to collaborative learning strategy in other to encourage social interaction, active engagement and positive interdependence among learners.
2. Also, teachers of biology should always use formative evaluation to identify areas where students have difficulties. This will help to alleviate the so-called weak students to gain mastery of learning contents.
3. Teachers should be encouraged and/or mandated to attend workshops and seminars to acquaint themselves with requisite skills to use mastery and collaborative learning approaches in classrooms.
4. Curriculum planners should design curriculum in such a way that, mastery and collaborative learning strategies can be used to fully implement biology curriculum.
5. Textbook writers should lay emphasis on students' activities that will promote the incorporation of collaborative learning strategy in biology textbook

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